

Long-term trends in body condition and timing of moult of shorebirds mirroring habitat status of the Dutch Wadden Sea

NLBIF project report

Jim de Fouw and Wim Fokker

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Stichting Calidris

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Background

Stichting Calidris is a volunteer organization that originated from wader research conducted by the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. Since 1968, research on waders in the Wadden Sea has been conducted on Schiermonnikoog, initially by the Vrije Universiteit, and since 1997, the monitoring research has continued under Stichting Calidris.

Every year in autumn, waders are captured, ringed, and measured. These data provide important insights into long-term changes in the distribution and timing of various wader populations. Additionally, long-term data on the biometry of waders can offer unique insights into their physical condition and, indirectly, the quality of their habitat in the Wadden Sea over an extended period.

Not all of these details have been digitized immediately after capture, making them inaccessible to the scientific community. In this project, we aim to digitize a long-term dataset of waders that has been collected since 1968. The collected data include, in addition to standard biometric measurements, detailed information on molting conditions. In the first phase of the project, all data from 1990 to 2023 will be digitized. In the second phase, all data from 1968 to 1990 will be digitized and published on GBIF. The first phase was completed in 2024, and the second phase will be published in 2025.

Data description

Data consist of a unique ring number linked to an individual shorebird of a certain species, in total nine of the most common shorebird species published on GBIF. Each record will hold an indication of the individual's age, moult status and sex (when possible to determine). The latter is scored via a standardised procedure (Prater et al. 1977). Per data record the following data is mobilised: individual ring number, date and time of caught bird, age and sex, biomass, biometric measurements (head size, bill size, tarsus length, leg size, wing length, etc.), state of primary wing feathers (score from old to new), state of plumage renewal (breeding to winter plumage) and estimate of active moult.

Data digitization, quality control and mobilisation

The procedure consists of three general steps: 1) data inventory, 2) data mobilisation and 3) data transfer and publication. During field campaigns the following procedure was followed: during ringing sessions all biometric measurements were recorded on different field forms over the years (see figure), which were stored and over the years partly digitised. All forms are well organised and stored in leaflets in a private storage.

- 1) During data inventory clarification of the status of the data gathered since 1990 was conducted. Data forms which were not digitised were separated and gathered for digitation.
- 2) Original field forms are scanned, digitised and stored in a digital cloud (by a professional agency). Specific algorithms were developed to digitise the scanned paper forms to excel format.
- 3) Data records undergo quality control by a researcher of the ringing group. During quality control the data was explored. A first outlier detection and possible mistakes were filtered out and checked with the original data scanned field forms and adjusted accordingly. A final statistical outlier analysis was conducted on the data. Finally, the data is transferred to GBIF in the Darwin Core data standard (dwc).

Figure. Overview of birds caught and ringed over the years published on GBIF. Note for some species numbers do not represent actual numbers ringed as records will be digitised in phase 2.

References

Prater, A. J., T. Prater, J. Marchant, and J. Vourinen. 1977. Guide to the identification and ageing of Holarctic waders. British Trust for Ornithology.